

Speculation on the Constancy of the Speed of Light in a Vacuum

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It is known that a photon is considered to have zero rest mass and a speed c which is the same when viewed from frames moving at different speeds. In this note, we speculate on the reason for this.

In (1), we suggested that there exists a solution to D'Alembertian $\phi = 0$ and D'Alembertian $A = 0$. We found solutions: $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ (1,1,1) leading to E and B fields perpendicular to each other and to the direction of motion, i.e. the x direction. Given that $-\omega t + kx$ appears to be a Lorentz invariant with $(\hbar k, \hbar \omega)$ being momentum and energy of an object with speed remaining unchanged (i.e. c remaining the same as seen from different moving frames), we find a particle-like object as a solution of a ϕ and A , electrostatic and electromagnetic potentials. This particle-like object is necessarily moving and has a wave dispersion relation $\omega/k = c$ (for $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ to be a solution of the D'Alembertian) and is a part of the potentials ϕ and A . Given that ϕ and A extend in space, a rest mass associated with this particle-like object would imply that there is a frame in which it is localized in a point-like region, whereas its localization region is the ϕ, A x-t spaces. Furthermore, even though $q\phi$ is a potential energy, there is no reason to suspect that ϕ is like a piece of rest mass, even though it transforms as one. It is linked with an electric field which is possibly a different sort of physical entity than a rest mass.

Thus, we argue that a photon is part of an electrostatic potential ϕ and a magnetic vector one A and even if it escapes and appears to be a point-particle, it is an unusual one because its confinement region is within a potential (form which it came), or in region in which it reflects between two mirrors etc. It is not constrained to any other local region which would imply a rest mass. This is equivalent to the statement that it is always moving. As a piece of moving potential, it is E and p which are important. The D'Alembertian equations for ϕ, A hold even for an accelerating charge, but the photon is still a solution of these equations which has nothing to do with the velocity or acceleration. The force accelerating the charge shows no signs of accelerating the particle-like object $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ or changing its speed. As a result, the photon must have the same vacuum speed as seen in any frame.

Origin of the Photon

A main source of photons in the macroscopic world is stars (e.g. the sun) or light bulbs. These, in turn, are linked to electrons being excited in an atom and then de-exciting, emitting photons. Thus, the photon seems to have an electromagnetic origin, unlike a particle with rest mass.

If this is indeed the case, we argue one should see photons in the electrostatic potential ϕ and magnetic vector potential A . We suggested in (1), that given the em equations:

$$\{-\text{grad dot grad} + 1/cc \text{ d/dt d/dt partial} \} \phi = (1/\epsilon_0) \text{ charge density} \quad ((1a))$$

$$\{-\text{grad dot grad} + 1/cc \text{ d/dt d/dt partial} \} A = \mu_0 \text{ current density} \quad ((1b))$$

one may find solutions by setting charge density and current density to 0, namely:

$$\Phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad A = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) (1,1,1) \quad ((2b))$$

if $\omega/k=c$.

This leads to E (electric) and B (magnetic) fields perpendicular to each other and the x direction. For the electric field $-d\Phi/dx$ partial cancels $-dA/dt$ partial in the x-direction.

$$B = \text{Grad} \times A \quad \text{yields} \quad B = \{0, -\exp(-i\omega t + ikx), \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)\} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, one has a particle-like object associated with $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ which at the same time is part of Φ and A.

One may note that $-\omega t + kx$ is a Lorentz invariant, i.e.

$$\text{Constant} = -\omega t + kx \rightarrow 0 = -\omega dt + k dx \quad \text{or} \quad \text{speed} = \omega/k \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{For a Lorentz transformation (3):} \quad \begin{matrix} |k'c| = |g & -gv/c| & |kc| \\ |w'| & |-gv/c & g| & |w| \end{matrix} \quad ((5)) \quad g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$$

$$k'c = gkc - gv\omega/c \quad \text{and} \quad w' = -gvk + g\omega \quad ((4b))$$

Using $\omega/k=c$ one has: $|w'/k'| = c$

An alternative way to examine this situation is to note that $EE = ppcc + momocccc$ ((5)), but to have $E/p = \text{speed}$ means that $m_0 = 0$ and speed is c. In this approach, one has a constant c speed a priori for the following reason. One may consider a particle with rest mass and obtain the Lorentz transformation matrix as one which transforms $(x=0, t) \rightarrow (x', t')$ such that $x'/t' = v$. The matrix should have dimensionless entries and so one writes v/b , where b is a constant with velocity units. In (2), we showed that for a moving charge one may prove that $b = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$ which is the speed of light in a vacuum. Given that ϵ_0, μ_0 are electromagnetic parameters which do not change when a charged object is viewed from different frames, c does not change either. The photon is a solution of Φ, A with no source, but must still comply with the EM environment which gives rise to the equations (D'Alembertians of Φ, A with no sources) which, in turn, lead to its solution.

Taking ((5)) which holds for an object with a rest mass, but is linked to electromagnetism nevertheless, there already exists a constant speed and wave dispersion relation if $m_0 = 0$.

Thus, c is an invariant because of the dispersion relation $\omega/k=c$ which follows from the D'Alembertian EM equation for Φ and A with the source set equal to 0. In other words, the association of a photon with Φ and A have a major influence on its properties.

Argument Based on Localization

Another way to consider the matter is to note that if a photon is part of a ϕ and A , it is localized within the region of ϕ and A . There is no extra information suggesting it should be localized within any smaller region. A rest mass, however, suggests such a localization. The notion of rest mass is localized energy with no motion. This does not seem to be the property one would like to have for a piece of energy which is part of a potential ϕ or A . The piece of energy can be anywhere in the ϕ , A region and so should always be in motion, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the invariance of the speed of light in a vacuum c and the photon's lack of a rest mass both come from the fact that it is part of the electrostatic potential ϕ and magnetic vector potential A , both of which are part of D'Alembertian equations: $\{-\text{grad dot grad} + 1/(cc) d/dt d/dt \text{ partial}\} \{\phi \text{ or } A\} = (1/e_0 \text{ charge density or } u_0 \text{ current density})$. A photon solution follows by setting sources equal to 0 and contains the factor $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$. In order for this to satisfy the D'Alembertian equations one must have the dispersion relation $\omega/k=c$ which is a wave-like dispersion. This is equivalent to the rest mass Lorentz invariant equation: $E^2 = pc^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ with $m_0=0$. Thus, there is a particle-like solution for ϕ , A from D'Alembertian equations with no source with $E = \hbar \omega$, $p = \hbar k$, which transform as four vectors, but for a $m_0=0$ situation.

We argue that there is a physical reason for $m_0=0$. Given that the photon is part of ϕ and A (for no sources in the D'Alembertian equations), this photon (particle-like object) is not confined to any small region of space, but should move all throughout the ϕ , A region. If the photon had a rest mass, one could find a frame in which it was at rest. The D'Alembertian equations would still hold, but one would have a piece of potential which was localized for no reason and not moving. We suggest that this would be unphysical. This implies that $m_0=0$ and $\omega/k=c$. The speed c is governed by electromagnetic parameters and given that there is no rest mass, it should not accelerate and so c should be the same for all frames (in a vacuum). Another way to say this is that the EM parameters ϵ_0 , μ_0 are invariants and they govern the speed of light value which thus makes it the same in all frames (in a vacuum).

References

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